

A Test-bench to Investigate the Use of Magnetic Fields for Haptic Feedback in Prosthetics

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Abstract—This abstract delves into the pivotal role of feedback in prosthetic devices and aims to investigate the validity of a novel approach based on magnetic interaction between appropriately powered solenoids and a magnet. Through controlled solenoid currents, the magnet exhibits movement along various directions, demonstrating the feasibility of utilizing this technique for providing feedback in prosthetic applications. The results highlight the potential of magnetic feedback as a promising avenue to enhance user experience and functionality in the field of prosthetics.

Index Terms—Feedback, Magnetic Field, Prosthetic Systems

I. INTRODUCTION

Prosthetic technology has witnessed remarkable advancements over the years, offering greater mobility and functionality to individuals with limb loss. One critical aspect contributing to the seamless integration of prosthetic devices into the user’s daily life is the incorporation of effective feedback mechanisms. Feedback plays a pivotal role in enhancing user experience, enabling intuitive control, and fostering a sense of embodiment with the artificial limb. As a result, innovative approaches have been explored to optimize feedback delivery in next-generation prostheses [1], [2]. The state-of-the-art in prosthetic feedback encompasses various techniques, including haptic sensors, force feedback, among others. While these methods have shown promising results, the quest for more natural and intuitive feedback persists. In recent years, the possibility of harnessing magnetic fields is being increasingly investigated: both for prosthetic control and providing feedback to the user. In one of the latest innovative approaches [3], the patient’s movements can be detected and translated into commands for the prosthesis. This allows for more natural and intuitive control of the artificial limb, significantly enhancing prosthetic control and adaptability. In [4], magnetic fields are used to track the position of implanted magnets to control prosthetic limbs. Moreover, recent studies suggest that integrating magnetic fields into haptic interfaces could modulate the activation of mechanoreceptors, enabling a more nuanced and

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Fig. 1. Experimental setup. **a.** the structure (in gray) houses three solenoids (in red) positioned beneath a layer of artificial skin (in pink). On top, a magnet (in brown) is placed, connected to a marker (in black); **b.** three solenoids strategically positioned for the manipulation of magnetic fields; **c.** a marker attached to the magnet enable precise tracking and analysis of movements of the magnet.

realistic haptic feedback experience: in the method proposed in [5], the stimulus provided by an induced field can act on the nerves and muscles around the mechanoreceptors, which can induce tactile sensations. The system in [6], by modulating the magnetic fields in response to sensory cues or external stimuli, can convey real-time feedback to the user. The current state of the art in the field has predominantly focused on the implementation of implanted magnets within muscles or externally applied devices on the skin, which indirectly deliver stimuli. In order to explore the feasibility and effectiveness of using magnetic feedback to improve user experience and prosthetic performance, a novel approach with a focus on the integration of magnetic field interaction with solenoids is discussed. An experimental setup is presented in Fig. 1, which involves three solenoids and a magnet placed above a layer of artificial skin. By properly controlling three solenoids to generate a desired magnetic field intensity, it will be demonstrated how the magnet can be manipulated to perform small movements along different directions on the artificial skin layer. Through a series of experiments and simulations, the precision and effectiveness of this approach in conveying real-time information are assessed. The results highlight the potential of this technology to significantly enhance prosthetic functionality and, consequently, user satisfaction.

The proof of concept presented here lays the groundwork for the development of more natural and intuitive prosthetic interfaces, shaping the future of assistive technologies in enhancing mobility and overall quality of life.

II. METHODOLOGY

In order to conduct an exhaustive exploration of the potential of controlling motion in subcutaneously implanted magnets to provide feedback, a novel approach is presented, which leverages the magnetic field generated by three solenoids to move a magnet placed beyond an artificial skin layer.

A. System setup

The aim is to illustrate the magnet's capacity for movement in various directions through modulation of the current in the solenoids. To accomplish this, a representation of the experimental setup is provided in Fig. 1.

In Fig. 1a, the structure (in gray) houses three solenoids (in red) positioned beneath a layer of artificial skin (in pink). On top, a magnet (in brown) is placed, connected to a marker (in black). Fig. 1b shows three solenoids mounted within a supporting structure strategically positioned for the manipulation of magnetic fields, showcasing the potential to induce controlled movements of magnets above the artificial skin layer (approximately 2mm thick). The solenoids employed are non-powered magnetic electromagnets with a holding force of 15N, meaning they attract the magnet only when not energized. The magnet, positioned on top, is mechanically constrained to a marker to facilitate better visualization of induced displacements, as depicted in Fig. 1c.

B. Experiments and Results

The objective of this study is to validate a novel approach for providing feedback through magnetic interaction, where displacements of a few millimeters were deemed sufficient for assessment.

To achieve this, two primary experiments were conducted, aiming to demonstrate the induced movement of the magnet along two main directions: the vertical direction and the horizontal direction. The rationale behind this choice lies in the potential of these types of movements to serve as a foundation for a wide range of feedback applications in the field of prosthetics.

In the first experiment, the three solenoids were supplied with an identical current (approximately 700mA peak-to-peak) to observe the vertical movement of the magnet. In the second experiment, an alternating current (approximately 750mA peak-to-peak) was applied to the solenoids to induce horizontal movement, causing the magnet to follow a circular trajectory. The outcomes of the experiments are depicted in Fig. 2. On the left, current waveforms for each solenoid are illustrated, while on the right, the magnet displacement is highlighted. The diagram visually portrays the temporal trajectory of the magnet displacement. The blue circular marker denotes the magnet position, while the corresponding black silhouette depicts the magnet displacement progression over a specified time interval. In the first experiment, as illustrated in Fig. 2a, the observed displacement recorded an approximate value of 0.5 mm along the vertical direction. In the subsequent experiment (Fig. 2b), the displacement spanning diverse directions manifested an approximate measure of 0.5 mm.

Fig. 2. Current waveforms for each solenoid and magnet displacement in two experimental setups. (a.) depicts the waveforms and magnet displacement along the vertical axis, and (b.) showcases the waveform and the displacement along a circular trajectory.

These displacements provide sufficient validation and demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed approach, showcasing the magnet's controlled movements and the potential for novel proprioceptive feedback.

III. CONCLUSION

In this study, successful manipulation of a magnet situated above an artificial skin layer was demonstrated, employing three solenoids positioned below. The magnet exhibited controlled movements both vertically and along circular trajectories, highlighting the potential of novel proprioceptive feedback approaches utilizing magnetic fields and implanted magnets. This emphasizes the significance of precise magnet manipulation for advancing prosthetic technologies. By refining control mechanisms and exploring innovative applications, this research opens pathways towards enhanced integration of prosthetic devices with the human body, empowering individuals with limb loss to achieve improved mobility and overall quality of life.

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